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Assessment of N95 Strap Placement Across Multiple Uses

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KEYWORDS

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Respirators (N95 FFRs);
Respirator Fit Testing;
Strap Placement;
Respiratory Protection;
Healthcare Workers;
Repeated Donning.

ABSTRACT

Proper fit and consistent use of N95 Filtering Facepiece Respirators are essential for protecting healthcare workers against airborne hazards. While N95 filtering face piece respirators are rigorously tested to meet regulatory testing requirements, such as filtration efficiency, loading and pressure differential, variations in strap placement and repeating donning can influence overall fit and protection. This study evaluated the fit factors of two NIOSH-approved N95 filtering facepiece respirator models, the 3M Aura and the 3M 1860, under standard manufacturer strap placement recommendations and an alternative crossed strap placement across multiple uses. Twenty-five participants completed eight quantitative fast fit tests using a TSI PortaCount® 8026 device, assessing fit factors across standard and crossed strap placement during two donnings. Two hundred total fit factors were collected and analyzed using paired t-tests to determine statistically significant difference between test conditions. Results revealed a statistically significant reduction in mean fit factors of the 3M 1860 model when straps were crossed ($p < 0.001$), particularly after repeated use. Repeated donning further impacted the fit factors of the 3M 1860 under crossed strap conditions ($p = 0.005$), indicating fit and performance degradation over time. While the 3M Aura also showed a decrease in fit factor with crossed straps, the change was not statistically significant ($p = 0.174$).

1. BACKGROUND

Respiratory protection is a primary component in safeguarding workers, especially in environments where airborne contaminants, pathogens, and particulates pose a health risk. With the increased prevalence of airborne diseases and environmental hazards, proper use of respirators, particularly N95 Filtering Facepiece Respirators (N95 FFRs) and equivalents, have gained heightened importance in both healthcare and industrial settings (Harber & Beckett, 2023).

As of 2022, 16.3 million people were employed in the healthcare industry (N. C. F. H. W. A. 2024). N95 FFRs are utilized to protect healthcare workers (HCWs), as these N95 FFRs provide a barrier between the person and airborne particulates. At least 95% of airborne particles, including harmful pathogens, smoke, dust, smoke and various other contaminants are filtered with an N95 FFRs. These respirators greatly reduce the risk of infection in a healthcare setting (Ejaz, et al., 2024). N95 FFRs have been used

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to protect workers from airborne diseases such as COVID-19, influenza, tuberculosis, and others by filtering out viral and bacterial particles and droplets. With inhalation as a primary exposure pathway, HCWs rely on protection from personal protective equipment (PPE), specifically respiratory protection.

Especially important in protecting HCWs is the use of a properly fitted and sealed respirator. Effective respiratory protection relies on using the appropriate type of mask, ensuring the respirator fits the wearer appropriately through a fit test, maintaining a seal, and following the manufacturer's recommendations, which significantly influences the respirator's performance. HCWs must select a respirator that fits well to their face and minimizes the amount of air leakage (NIOSH Myths, 2016).

The population of workers that need respiratory protection has a wide variation of face shapes and sizes. For this reason, it is critical to provide an array of N95 FFR styles to match to the unique dimensions of a person's face. A study by Rottach and Lei (2018) found that a "poor match between the face and the respirator can allow excessive leakage of unfiltered air into the breathing space". Common N95 FFR models used in healthcare settings are trifold and cup shaped models. One particular cup shaped model, the surgical N95 FFRs, is manufactured to meet both National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) N95 FFR testing standards and Food and Drug Administration standards for surgical masks (Smith et al., 2016)

Face seal leakage can enable fine respiratory particles to bypass mask filters (Ejaz et al., 2024). A study comparing non-fitted with fitted N95 FFRs utilized in a healthcare environment, determined that HCWs using fitted N95 FFRs, had lower outcomes of respiratory type illness and infection than the HCW wearing non fitted N95 FFRs (Regli, et al., 2021).

An initial fit test is performed to validate and ensure the respirator make and model is an appropriate fit for the wearer by passing respirator fit factor (FF) requirements. A passing FF for an N95 FFR is a minimum of 100, indicating a good fit. The fit tests are accomplished through qualitative or quantitative methods. Both qualitative and quantitative fit test method follows series of exercises which determines if the respirator meets fit testing requirements and indicates that a respirator is a good fit for the wearer. Qualitative fit test methods rely on the users senses and are based on a pass or fail depending on whether they taste the testing agent (OSHA, 2004). If the individual cannot sense the testing agent it is determined that the minimum FF of 100 for the N95 FFR is met. Quantitative methods calculate a fit factor for each individual exercise based on particle concentration inside and outside of the respirator. While using quantitative methods such as the TSI PortaCount® 8026, fit factors are calculated and must receive an overall fit factor of 100, however can determine FFs levels up to 200. FF above 200 show as 200+, indicating a stronger fit.

Healthcare workers routinely work 8–12-hour shifts and may readjust respirators, ultimately modifying the fit throughout a workday. In a study done by Suen, et al., (2019), it was found that even after just 10 minutes of "normal nursing procedures", the respirators FF decreased by as much as 50. Masks may also shift due to biological factors such as normal sweat and skin oils being produced along with facial changes. During a normal shift a person's face may slightly swell due to hydration, fatigue, or pressure from wearing a mask for long periods of time (Ejaz et al., 2024).

Several studies have investigated how typical workplace practices and repeated donning affect the overall FF of respirators. Straps may move during a work shift due to extended wear, frequent movement, PPE layering, or reuse. Since N95 FFR are frequently removed and reapplied throughout a shift, understanding the impact of multiple donnings on fit integrity is critical. The straps of N95 FFRs are composed of various elastomeric materials designed to stretch and recoil; however, once stretched beyond their elastic limit, their ability to return to their original form diminishes, potentially compromising the respirator's fit (Roberg et al., 2012).

NIOSH found that many HCWs used improper practices when donning respirators, including incorrect strap placement, dismissing a user seal check, improper doffing, and improper respirator disposal (NIOSH Myths, 2016). NIOSH (2023) provides instructions on proper donning and correct strap placement of N95 FFRs. Wearers are instructed to place the bottom of the N95 FFR under the chin with the nosepiece bar located at the bridge of the nose. NIOSH recommends to pull the top strap over your head, then move the bottom strap over the head with the upper strap placed on the crown of the head and the lower strap behind the neck and under hair where needed (Cummings et al., 2007). Ensuring proper upper and lower strap placement results in the correct force and pull on the N95 FFR to keep the placement on the face and chin (Niezgoda et al., 2013 and Roberg et al., 2012).

A study completed on the effect of upper strap downward displacement found that the slippage of upper strap placement has little negative effect on the overall fit factor (Roberge et al., 2014). NIOSH (2023) also notes the importance of not wearing the straps in a crisscross, which will change the placement of the N95 FFR.

The purpose of this research is to investigate fit factors of two N95 FFR models based on standard and crossed strap placement across multiple uses. Because they are commonly used in healthcare, both 3M Aura 9210+ and 3M 1860 models were utilized for this project. The proposed research specific aims and hypothesis are described below:

Specific Aim 1:

Evaluate the fast-fit test results of N95 models while following the standard manufacture strap placement recommendations with fast fit test results of crossed strap placement.

- *Null Hypothesis 1 – There will be no difference in the fit test results of the N95 respirators while straps are in the manufacturer suggested location when compared to respirators fit tested with a crossed strap placement.*

Specific Aim 2:

Evaluate the fast-fit test results of N95 models while following manufacture strap placement recommendations with fast fit test results of crossed strap placement across multiple uses.

- *Null Hypothesis 2 – There will be no difference in the fit test results of the N95 respirators while straps are in the manufacturer suggested location across multiple uses.*

Specific Aim 3:

Compare the fast-fit test results of both N95 models with manufacture strap placement recommendations and with crossed strap placement across multiple uses.

- *Null Hypothesis 3 – There will be no difference in the fit test results of the N95 respirators while straps are in a crossed placement across multiple uses.*

2. METHODS

For this investigation, 25 study subjects were recruited to assess the fit of two 3M N95 FFR models using two strap placements. Straps placed in the manufacturers recommended location is referred to as “standard” location, and strap placed in a crisscrossed position is referred as “crossed” location. This research was reviewed and granted approval by the University of Montana Institutional Review Board for the use of human subjects as participants.

Participants were instructed to arrive with a clean-shaven face and were instructed not to smoke for 30 minutes prior to the fit tests. Participants were also instructed on proper donning and doffing of the respirators and strap placement for each fit test. Additionally, participants were informed of the test exercises and how to perform the exercises prior to beginning the fit test. Lastly participants were given the opportunity to stop the test at any point for any reason.

Materials utilized for this research included two N95 FFR's manufactured by 3M; an Aura 9210 + (Aura) and a 3M surgical N95. The 3M Aura 9210+ is a trifold one-size fits most respirator and the 3M 1860 is a cup shape model, also known as the surgical N95. Each model has different strap materials, the Aura straps are composed of a polyisoprene band and the 1860 contains a braided polyester made from four connected bands.

Additional materials utilized were a probing kit, a TSI PortaCount® 8026, a TSI particle generator, and TSI fitPro+ software. Fit testing was completed with the TSI PortaCount® 8026 while using the N95 fast fit test method, which utilizes four exercises. A particle generator was used to ensure the particle count was sufficient while remaining under the recommended 800 pt/cc (TSI, 2022).

Each of the participants completed eight total fit tests; two fit tests were completed with each strap placement, standard and crossed, with each respirator model. Study subjects were fit tested two times in each strap placement for both respirator models to determine fit factors across strap placement and across multiple donning, using a total of four respirators, one respirator for standard placement and one for crossed strap placement for each FFR model. With each respirator model, a fast-fit test was completed with the standard manufacturer strap placement, the respirator was then removed and donned a second time for a second fit test with standard strap placement. With a new and unused N95 FFR, the test subject then underwent the same process with crossed straps. The process was completed again with the second 3M Model. Strap placement is shown in figure 1 and 2 for each N95 FFR model.

A total FF was obtained for each of the eight fit tests and FFs were collected for each test exercise. The aim of this study was to compare the total FF of the two different mask styles for the standard strap placement versus the crossed strap placement across multiple uses. Paired T tests were completed to analyze and compare the datasets. Eight different sets of data were analyzed and compared to determine if there was a statistically significant difference in fit factors. Minitab software was used in the analysis.

Figure 1. *3M Aura Standard and Crossed Strap Placement*

Figure 2. 3M 1860 Standard and Crossed Strap Placement

3. RESULTS

The aim of this study was to compare total FF of two different N95 FFR styles with standard versus crossed strap placement. A total of 800 FFs were collected, with 200 total FF. Total FFs were calculated based on the FF of each of the four test exercises of the fast fit test. The initial fit test using the Aura with standard strap placement had the highest pass rating percentage of 88 %. The subsequent standard strap fit test with the Aura showed a slight decrease in pass rating percentage of 84 %, which is the same passing percentage rate as the first fit test with the crossed straps using the Aura. The second set of fit tests with the Aura and crossed straps showed a pass percentage of 76 %, eight percent lower from the first fit test with the crossed straps.

The performance of the 1860, as measured by the quantitative fit test, demonstrated a reduced pass rate as compared to the Aura. The initial 1860 fit test with standard straps had a pass rating of 52 %, while the second fit test with the standard strap declined to a pass percentage of 40 %. With the crossed straps, there was an additional reduction in the fit factor pass rate. The first donning with crossed straps showed a pass rate of 24%. The lowest pass rating was with the second donning of the 1860 with crossed straps, with a pass rate of 12%. The progression fit factors for each dataset are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Fit Factor Pass Percentage

A paired t-test was used to analyze and compare the different data sets.

- a) Standard vs Crossed 1st Donning Aura
- b) Standard vs Crossed 1st Donning 1860
- c) Standard 1st vs 2nd Donning Aura
- d) Standard 1st vs 2nd Donning 1860
- e) Crossed 1st vs 2nd Donning Aura
- f) Crossed 1st vs 2nd Donning 1860
- g) Standard Aura vs 1860 1st Donning
- h) Crossed Aura vs 1860 1st Donning
- i) Standard Aura vs 1860 2nd Donning
- j) Crossed Aura vs 1860 2nd Donning

3.1 Standard Versus Crossed Straps

When comparing standard strap placement to crossed strap placement for Aura first donning, the results yielded a p-value of 0.174, indicating no significant difference. As shown in figure 4, the mean fit factor for Aura standard strap placement was 176.92, with a standard deviation of 49.74. Aura crossed strap placement had a mean fit factor of 157.6, with a standard deviation of 51.96.

Figure 4. Interval Plot of Aura Standard 1, Aura Crossed 1

The results of comparing strap placement of the 1860, first donning, yielded a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating significant difference. Here, the mean FF for the 1860 with standard strap placement had a mean FF of 115.36, with a standard deviation of 63.83. The 1860 with crossed strap placement had a mean FF of 65.32 with a standard deviation of 60.75. This is shown below in figure 5.

Figure 5. Interval Plot of 1860 Standard 1, 1860 Crossed 1

3.2 First donning versus second Donning

When comparing first and second donning of N95 FFRs, the following data were collected.

After comparing first donning of Aura with standard placement to the second donning a p-value of 0.614 was yielded. As shown in figure 6, the first donning of the Aura with standard strap placement had a mean FF of 176.92 with a standard deviation of 49.74, the second donning had a mean FF of 170.96 with a standard deviation of 48.52.

Figure 6. Interval Plot of Aura Standard 1, Aura Standard 2

Comparing the first donning of 1860 with standard placement to the second donning yielded a p-value of 0.186. As shown in figure 7, the first donning of the 1860 with standard placement had a mean FF of 115.36 with a standard deviation of 63.83. The second donning had a mean FF of 104.96 with a standard deviation of 56.03.

Figure 7. Interval Plot of 1860 Standard 1, 1860 Standard 2

As shown in figure 8, the first donning of the Aura with crossed straps compared to the second donning of the Aura with crossed straps yielded a p-value of 0.522. The first donning with crossed straps had a mean FF of 157.6 with a standard deviation of 51.96. The second donning with crossed straps had a mean FF of 149.24 with a standard deviation of 65.30.

Figure 8. Interval Plot of Aura Crossed 1, Aura Crossed 2

As depicted in figure 9, the first donning of the 1860 with crossed straps, when compared to the second donning of the 1860 with crossed straps, yielded a p-value of 0.005. The first donning with crossed straps had a mean FF of 65.32, with a standard deviation of 60.75. The second donning with crossed straps had a mean FF of 42.64, with a standard deviation of 46.75.

Figure 9. Interval Plot of 1860 Crossed 1, 1860 Crossed 2

3.3 Comparing Aura versus 1860 style respirators 1st Donning

The first donning of the Aura with standard straps, when compared to the first donning of the 1860 with standard straps, yielded a p-value < 0.001. This comparison can be shown in figure 10.

Figure 10. Interval Plot of Standard Aura 1, Standard 1860 1

The first donning of the Aura with crossed straps, when compared to the first donning of the 1860 with crossed straps yielded a p-value < 0.001. This comparison can be shown in figure 11.

Figure 11. Interval Plot of Crossed Aura 1, Crossed 1860 1

3.4 Comparing Aura versus 1860 style respirators 2nd Donning

The second donning of the Aura with standard straps, when compared to the second donning of the 1860 with standard straps, yielded a p-value < 0.001. This comparison can be shown in figure 12.

Figure 12. Interval Plot of Standard Aura 2, Standard 1860 2

The second donning of the Aura with crossed straps, when compared to the second donning of the 1860 with crossed straps, yielded a p-value < 0.001. This comparison can be shown in figure 13.

Figure 13. Interval Plot of Crossed Aura 2, Crossed 1860 2

4. DISCUSSION

This study showed a statistically significant difference in fit factors when comparing the FF of the 1860 standard strap placement and crossed strap placement. The statistically significant comparisons involved the 1860-style respirators, indicating that the use of the manufacturer's recommendations for strap placement is critical. The Aura-style respirators proved to decrease FFs when comparing standard to crossed strap placement, although it was not statistically significant.

A study completed by Roberge et al., (2012) looked at the elastic restorative forces after being stretched from the initial and subsequent donning. The study findings revealed the largest decrease in strap stretch loss was in the first donning, although the degradation continued to decline slightly through multiple donnings (Roberge et al., 2012). These results indicated that the load decrements would be sufficient to pass a fit test of up to 5 donnings; however, they did not verify with human subjects. Bergman et al. (2012) tested six N95 models and found that multiple donning had a negative effect on the overall FF of N95 FFRs. However, the results were dependent on the type of N95 model tested. The data found suggests that a total of five consecutive donnings can be performed before the FF will consistently fall below 100, leaving HCWs unprotected (Bergman et al., 2012).

Roberge et al. (2014) compared the fit factors of three cup-shaped N95 FFR models and one tri-fold N95 FFR with the standard strap placement and an alternative placement with the top strap displaced downward over the ears. Similar to this study, the Roberge et al. (2014) study showed reduced fit factors with the displaced strap placement. Also, the initial fit test results were lower with the cupped type of mask than with the trifold. However, Roberge et al. (2014) found that the displaced alternative straps fit test did not significantly decrease from those that passed the initial fit test. When comparing results of this study, the initial fit test results were also lower for the cup shaped mask in comparison with the trifold mask. The trifold showed 88% of the initial fit test with standard strap placement period of those that passed the initial fit with standard strap placement, 82% past the crossed strap placement fit test for the first donning. Looking at the 1860, cup style, only 52% of the initial fit test with standard strap placement passed. Of those that passed the initial fit with the standard strap placement, 38.5% passed the crossed strap replacement fit test for the first donning.

It is also important to note that it is recognized that there may be significant variability in face morphology in human subjects and that not all mask styles are compatible with all subjects. The Aura had an overall higher passing fit test for both standard and crossed straps vs. the 1860 model, where the percentage of those who passed the initial fit test was low, indicating the 1860 was not a good fit for 48% of the participants. Like the Roberge (2014) findings, test subjects who were considered petite were more likely to not pass the quantitative fit test, particularly when using the 1860 style respirator.

It was also found that initial improper upper strap placement can occur due to a number of factors. These include human error, friction of the straps and hair, head motion, speech, and speed in which exercise are completed. Friction of straps and hair can occur due to composition of FFR straps, natural oiliness of hair, hair moisture, the products an individual may use, and the hair style worn by the individual.

5. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Several limitations were noted throughout the study. The sample size was small and is not representative of other populations. Study participants were a convenience sample of college students recruited at the university, they were not selected randomly and do not represent the larger population. Upper strap location had variances from participant to participant and across participants, which may have influenced the total FF. Some study subjects were more susceptible to strap slippage during the exercises, this may have influenced seal, creating a leakage and thus affected our findings. Potential variations in tubing and probe connections were present and in the port positioning. Specifically, the 1860 mask style had reduced initial and all subsequent fit for all participants indicating the need for larger sample size. The low initial fit and subsequent fit tests were likely due to the variations in individual face structures and size. This mismatch may have influenced overall fit test results and limited the general findings across the study.

An increased sample size is recommended in future studies to enhance statistical power, facilitate the detection of outliers, and improve the accuracy and reliability of the results. More participants would help ensure the externalization of findings. In addition, study subjects should be randomly selected from the population of interest to be representative of the target population, thus increasing the generalizability of the study's conclusions.

Another aspect of the study design to consider is the exact location of the upper strap placement. Achieving uniform strap placement among all participants is difficult, given the variability in head and face anatomy and the potential for minor deviations during application. To improve the consistency and reliability of future measurements, it is recommended that a standardized method or positioning guide be developed to ensure uniform strap placement on participants' heads. The variability in strap positioning may influence the seal and thus the measurements collected. Consistency of strap placement would likely minimize variability and enhance results.

Our study completed two donnings per strap location. Data from additional donnings would be useful to determine fit degradation over subsequent donnings and allow further comparisons with studies that included five or more donnings.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluated the impact of N95 strap placement across multiple uses. The results demonstrated a statistically significant difference in the overall FF when the straps of the 3M 1860 N95 respirator were crossed, particularly after two consecutive donnings. These findings highlight the critical importance of adhering to manufacturer-recommended strap placement, especially for the 1860 model. Future research

could expand on these findings by increasing the sample size and developing a standardized method for upper strap positioning

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